

Professionals' perception of the development process of AI-based systems

Introduction

- **Potential Users:** Professionals' works in the development process of AI-based systems.
- **Interview Objectives:** Our focus is to understand that as a professional in the industry working on the agile development of AI-based systems. We would like to hear your opinion on (i) the roles involved, (ii) the essential skills required, (iii) your relationship with others roles, and (iv) your experience working in software development teams.

Interview Script

1. Profile Professional and Pessoal

- a. Gender
- b. Age
- c. Role in the company
- d. Experience in the role
- e. Role seniority
- f. Company Location
- g. Company Size

2. AI Systems Insights, Development Process and Roles

- a. **What type of AI system is developed in your company?**
 - i. an intelligent component developed in software;
 - ii. an intelligent service that provides some resource to one or more software;
 - iii. an entire software of AI or
 - iv. an AI embedded in hardware devices accessed by software.
- b. **What technique(s) have you used in the development of AI systems?**
- c. **What methodology is used in the AI systems development process?**
- d. **What roles exist in your company?**

3. Activities, Skills and Collaboration

- a. **How often do you perform activities in the development of AI Systems, considering your role?** (Answer using the Likert Scale - (1) Never, (2) Rarely, (3) Occasionally, (4) Frequently and (5) Very often)
- i. Explore the problem to be solved (prediction, classification, optimization, computer vision).
 - ii. Identify and specify requirements considering the characteristics of the types of AI problems and algorithms.
 - iii. Model complex processes and interconnected systems, essential for specifying requirements in systems that include intelligent components.
 - iv. Design interfaces that provide adequate feedback on AI operations, including the explainability of AI decisions to end users.
 - v. Incorporate ethical considerations into the design of AI systems.
 - vi. Design AI components as independent services that can be integrated into larger systems, facilitating maintenance and updating.
 - vii. Design systems that efficiently manage large volumes of data, essential for training and inference in AI models. This includes considerations for data storage, processing, and flow.
 - viii. Foster collaboration among team members from different areas, such as software engineering, data science, and design, ensuring everyone can contribute effectively.
 - ix. Adapt agile practices to accommodate intelligent systems development's iterative and experimental nature.
 - x. Work with large volumes of data, including experience with AI-specific databases and processing tools.
 - xi. Work with manipulating, analyzing, and visualizing data related to the optimization problem, supporting the tuning and validation of evolutionary models.
 - xii. Develop strategies to test AI models' accuracy, reliability, and performance, including unit testing of AI code and model validation.
 - xiii. Implement tools and processes to automate testing of AI components, considering the probabilistic and non-deterministic nature of AI models.

b. Indicate 3 knowledge that you consider most important, taking into account your role, for the development of an AI system.

- i. Understanding the types of problems that AI can solve.
- ii. Understanding the data required to train AI models.
- iii. Understanding the complexity and development time associated with AI systems.
- iv. Understanding the basic principles of data collection, analysis, and interpretation is crucial, as intelligent systems depend on the quality of data for training and validation.
- v. Understanding the ethical considerations, data privacy, and legal regulations related to the use of AI.
- vi. Understanding the business needs for specific technical requirements for AI, including accuracy, acceptable latency, and computational costs.
- vii. Understanding AI principles, algorithms, and technologies is essential to choose the most appropriate approaches.
- viii. Understanding how to create effective application programming interfaces (APIs) for integrating AI components, enabling communication and data exchange between different system parts.
- ix. Understanding basic AI concepts, algorithms, and tools to develop AI systems.
- x. Understanding distributed and parallel computing to optimize AI model training and inference.
- xi. Knowledge of integrating AI components into user interfaces, creating experiences that clearly communicate AI functionality and interact intuitively with users.

c. How often do you interact with existing roles in your company?
(Answer using the Likert Scale - (1) Never, (2) Rarely, (3) Occasionally, (4)Frequently and (5) Very often)**d. Indicate the main challenges experienced during the development of AI systems.****Closing**

Thank you for your participation. Your experience and insights are essential for delineating roles and collaborating in the development process of AI-based systems. If you have additional thoughts after the session, please share them.